

Creating Composites that Fail More Gradually

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Carbon/epoxy composites: STIFF, STRONG

BUT failure is SUDDEN & CATASTROPHIC

Can we add metal-like DUCTILITY?

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**High Performance
Ductile Composite Technology-
HiPerDuCT Programme**

The HiPerDuCT Challenge

To create high performance composites that show ductile or pseudo-ductile response

Ductility

- Ability to deform nonlinearly without fracture
 - To achieve more gradual failure
 - To redistribute load at stress concentrations
- Ideally no loss of elastic modulus – true ductility
- Shorter term target: pseudo-ductility with loss of modulus due to damage
- Increased toughness, energy absorption are additional benefits
- Change in secant modulus is key
- Elastic-perfectly “plastic” is ideal
 - maximises load redistribution
- Initial focus on tension, but stiffness and strength in other loading modes must be maintained

Mechanisms for creating gradual failure

- Fibre reorientation - using excess length e.g. angle plies
- Distributed damage e.g. ply fragmentation
- Aligned discontinuous composites – slip at interfaces
- Ductile fibres

Mechanisms for Pseudo-Ductility

Fragmentation in hybrid laminates

Pseudo-ductile hybrid composites

High strain material

Low strain material

Hybrid

Damage modes in hybrids

- Damage may develop in 4 different ways:

1. Premature high strain material failure

2. Single delamination

3. Low strain material fragmentation

4. Low strain material fragmentation and delamination

X Catastrophic failure

✓ Gradual failure

Damage mode maps for UD hybrids

**0.15 mm glass plies
0.03 mm thin carbon**

**Jalalvand, Czél,
Wisnom, 2015**

S-glass / thin TR30 carbon hybrid

Czél, Jalalvand, Wisnom, 2016a

Hybrid cyclic tests

- Up to 1.5% strain fully reversible – no damage
- Subsequently small amount of hysteresis
- Progressive loss of stiffness as fragmentation progresses
- Increase in stress once fragmentation has saturated

1SG/1MR40/1SG
Hexcel S-glass/913, 0.15 mm
Skyflex intermediate modulus
carbon/epoxy, 0.06 mm

Wisnom, Fuller,
Suwarda, Czél, 2015

All carbon hybrid - T1000/XN80/T1000

Czél et al, 2017

UD hybrids - Compression

- Bending of glass/epoxy beam with M55 carbon/S-glass hybrid on surface
- M55 carbon layer fragments

Surface view

Side view

Hybridisation in QI laminates

- UD hybridisation: $[45_H/90_H/-45_H/0_H]_s$
- Material dispersed
- QI hybridisation: $[QI_G/QI_C/QI_G]_s$
- Orientation dispersed

 Glass
 Carbon
EPSRC
Engineering and Physical Sciences
Research Council

Quasi-isotropic pseudo-ductile laminate

- $[QI_{G60}/QI_{C60}]_s$ tested in 0, 60 and -60 directions.

$[60_G/-60_G/0_G/0_C/60_C/-60_C]_s$

Dispersed delamination

Fragmentation

Fotouhi, Jalalvand,
Wisnom, 2017a

 S2-Glass – 0.15 mm

 T300 Carbon – 0.03 mm

Suppressing stress concentrations

- Open-hole tension and sharp notches

Fotouhi, Jalalvand, Wisnom, 2017b

Other loading conditions

- Off-axis tension at 5, 10 & 20°

- Indentation and impact: Different from conventional composites. Interesting behavior - under investigation

- Fatigue: No significant damage for loads up to 80% of fragmentation initiation strain after 100k cycles for UD and QI hybrids

A new accurate simple tensile test

- Standard methods tend to underestimate tensile strength due to stress concentrations at grips
- Hybrids can eliminate stress concentration
- Fail in gauge section at much higher strain
- 1.86% vs. 1.5% for TR30 carbon
- Gauge section failure even without end-tabs
- Gives correct baseline strain, enables proper evaluation of hybrid effect

Hybrid effect

- Hybrid effects may be overestimated due to incorrect baseline
- There is a significant effect, but only for very thin plies
- Due to constraint on critical cluster formation

← Baseline strain from delaminating hybrids

Skyflex TR30
carbon/epoxy

Wisnom et al, 2016b

Hybrid effect

Pseudo-ductile hybrids can take advantage of a greater proportion of the carbon fibre strength distribution

Overload sensing

Ordinary photos, NOT special NDT

- Load carrying surface layer or bonded patch
- Strain can be tuned by choice of fibre
- Wireless and offline
- No special training required

Wisnom, Czél, Jalalvand, Potter 2016

Fatigue cycle indicator

- Can also be applied to monitor subsequent cyclic loading
- After initial fracture, sensor ply will gradually delaminate
- Linear relation between damage and number of cycles

Increasing number of cycles

Suwarta, Fotouhi and Jalalvand

Overloaded bicycle handlebar

EN14781 Standard load:
1000 N

Applied load: 2700 N

Damage visualised at:
1750 N

Hybrid repair patch - Concept

Application of appearance change of glass-carbon hybrids to give warning of overload or crack propagation in Al panel.

Initial crack = 20 mm
 $\sigma_{\max} = 110$ MPa

Repaired with hybrid
[SG/UHM/SG]

Warning overload at $\sigma = 190$ MPa
and further crack extension

Michael Wu

Mechanisms for Ductility/Pseudo-Ductility

Reorientation of angle-ply

Reorientation of angle-ply

- Fibre reorientation has potential to create significant additional strain
- Angle plies usually fail prematurely
 - Matrix cracking
 - Free-edge delamination
- Reducing ply thickness reduces energy release rate, delaying delamination
- Ply thickness of 0.03 mm can completely suppress delamination and allow significant non-linearity

>20° reorientation of ±45° laminate before failure

Thin ply $[\pm 45]_{5S}$ laminates

- Skyflex high strength carbon/epoxy prepreg
- $t = 0.029$ mm, 22 g/m²
- $V_f = 42\%$, $E = 102$ GPa
- Damage suppressed
- Ductile response with necking, despite brittle fibres and resin
- 20% axial strain
- 350 MPa strength
- Low modulus < 10 GPa

Fuller and Wisnom, 2015

$(\pm 26_5)_s$ Cyclic tests

- Unloading - reloading tests follow monotonic response
- Substantial hysteresis, permanent deformation
- Initially appears to show a loss of modulus

Fuller and Wisnom, 2017

Normalised reloading modulus 0 – 360 MPa

- No reduction on initial modulus for $(\pm 26_5)_s$ or $(\pm 27_5)_s$
- Ductile not pseudo-ductile

Mechanisms for Pseudo-Ductility

Fragmentation in angle-plyies

Fragmentation in angle plies

Thin ply angle-ply laminates:

- Highly non-linear stress-strain behaviour
- Delaminations suppressed

Glass-Carbon hybrid laminates:

- $[G_n/C_m/G_n]$ layups
- Gradual failure via fragmentation of thin carbon plies

Combine mechanisms:

- Replace glass by angle ply carbon
- Fragmentation and fibre rotation

Fuller, Jalalvand, Wisnom, 2016

Carbon-epoxy, 0.03 mm plies, $[\pm 26_5/0]_S$

$(\pm 26_5/0)_s$ Cyclic response

- Unloading - reloading tests follow monotonic response
- Similar hysteresis, permanent deformation

Normalised reloading modulus

Small reduction in modulus 0 – 400 MPa due to fragmentation

Mixed carbon types [$\pm 25/0/\pm 25$]

- Ultra-high modulus 0° plies, intermediate modulus $\pm 25^\circ$
- 1.6% pseudo-ductile strain, modulus of 135 GPa
- Sub-laminate potentially only 0.15 mm thick

Wu et al, 2017

Open-hole tension

- Open-hole thin ply laminates.
- Often brittle failure with no load redistribution.
- Ductile thin ply laminates can redistribute stress.

Notch Insensitive

Tension-tension fatigue

- Tensile fatigue testing at a frequency of 2Hz, R ratio of 0.1 with various peak loads.
- CT-scans shows no damage after cycling at 80% of σ_{yield} .

- Can be operated at up to 80% of σ_{yield} for 100,000 cycles.

Tubular tension member

- Tensile testing

- Dimensions: 350 mm x \varnothing 55 mm
- Skyflex thin carbon, $[\pm 26_6/0]_s$

- Bolted joint configuration.
- Video extensometry for strains.

Fuller and Summers

Pseudo-ductility successfully demonstrated.

Mechanisms for Pseudo-Ductility

Discontinuous composites

Ductility in discontinuous composites

- Short fibres, platelets...
- Maintain high alignment
- Slip at interfaces
- Matrix plasticity

Discontinuous carbon prepreg

Czél et al 2015

High Performance Discontinuous Fibres

- HiPerDiF discontinuous fibre alignment method using water
- Enables high volume fraction and high degree of alignment
- Flexibility to combine different fibre types, lengths...

Fibre orientation head

High performance

Carbon/epoxy composites
(Fibre length: 3 mm, vf: 55%)
 $E \approx 115$ GPa, $\sigma_T \approx 1500$ MPa

Yu, Potter, Wisnom, 2014

Intermingled / intra-ply hybrids

High modulus carbon/E-glass epoxy, $v_f \approx 35 \sim 40\%$

Stress-strain curves of aligned short fibre composites can vary depending on the hybridisation type.

Intermingled

Intraply hybrid preforms

Yu, Longana, Jalalvand, Potter, Wisnom, 2015

Virtual testing framework

Model features:

- Full specimen modelled
- Stochastic fibre strengths
- Fibre breaks
- Non-linear matrix behaviour
- Hybrid reinforcement
 - Stiffness and diameter
- Fracture-based failure criterion

→
increasing strain

Finley and Pimenta

Optimising strength and ductility

- Isolate low-elongation fibres from one-another to minimise the size of critical clusters.
- Minimising cluster size maximises the strength and ductility of hybrid discontinuous composites.
- Future work will look at manufacturing this fibre arrangement using HiPerDiF.

intermingled

blocked

isolated fibre

High performance recycled composites

Enables closed loop recycling

Fluffy, short fibres

Aligned fibres

Recycling!

Key technology in remanufacturing

High level of alignment
↕
High fibre volume fraction
↕
High mechanical performance

~35% Vf

Longana, Ong, Yu, Potter, 2016

Potential further applications

For AFP application

Coriolis

Reduction of stress concentration at the ply drop

Through-thickness tapered end

High deformability – increase capability of steering

Stretched during the steering

For Additive Manufacturing (3D printing)

Adapting the HiPerDiF process to the production of aligned short fibre reinforced thermoplastic **towpreg** for **3D printing devices**.

Markforged

High performance ductile fibres

Single wall carbon nanotubes offer high strength and stiffness, high strain to failure, if chemistry and processing are optimised

Modulus : ~45 GPa
Strength : up to 1400 MPa
Strain : up to 60 %

Lee and Shaffer

Benefits of Ductility and Pseudo-Ductility

- Warning of overload or impending failure: non-catastrophic damage, detectable stiffness change
- Ability to still carry load after “failure initiation” until structure can be repaired or replaced
- Potential to be able to exploit a greater proportion of the fibre’s ultimate strain
- Load redistribution around stress concentrations provides notch insensitivity
- Potentially less defect sensitive
- Greater energy absorption

Conclusions - hybrids

- Ply fragmentation in thin-ply hybrids creates a pseudo-ductile response
- Can take advantage of the hybrid effect
- Fragmentation also in compression
- Multi-directional QI pseudo-ductility
- Notch insensitivity – similar unnotched and open hole QI strengths
- Can use for overload sensing

Increasing number of cycles

Conclusions - other approaches

- Fibre reorientation in thin-ply angle plies creates additional strain
- Can be combined with ply fragmentation
- Notch insensitive response
- HiPerDiF creates highly aligned, high V_f short fibre composites
- Can optimise pseudo-ductile response with different fibres and architectures
- Potential for high value products from recycled fibres
- High performance ductile CNT fibres created
- Opens up exciting new possibilities for composites that fail more gradually

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